

A Sense Of Cohesion And Its Relationship To Strain Management Strategies Among Kindergarten Teachers

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 14, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 14, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Sense of Cohesion, Stressful Situations And Kindergarten Teachers</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4947542</p>	<p><i>Many scholars believe that the sense of cohesion is the main pillar in the formation and building of the organic and psychological system of the individual, as it works directly as a filter when representing and inputting information about the individual's ability to absorb life's pressures and psychological symptoms. Accordingly, the current research aimed to identify:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A sense of cohesion among kindergarten teachers. 2. Strategies for coping with stress among kindergarten teachers. 3. The direction and strength of the relationship between a sense of cohesion and strategies for coping with pressures among kindergarten teachers. 4. The significance of the difference in the correlation between a sense of cohesion and strategies for coping with stress among kindergarten teachers according to the variables of social status (married - unmarried), years of service (10 years and less - more than 10 years). 5. The extent to which the sense of cohesion contributes to the strategies of coping with pressures among kindergarten teachers. <p><i>In her study, the researcher relied on the descriptive correlative approach. The sample of the statistical analysis consisted of (400) female teachers who were chosen by stratified random method from four directorates, and they applied the two research tools: a sense of cohesion and strategies for coping with stress.</i></p> <p><i>Then the researcher built a measure of sense of coherence, which consisted of three domains (feelings of clarity (the ability to understand), feelings of flexibility (the ability to manage), and feelings of significance (meaning), and its validity and stability were verified by extracting honesty by the method of apparent honesty. As for the stability, it was extracted by re-testing method and it reached (0.83) and the Facronbach coefficient (0.81) and accordingly, the measure of sense of cohesion in its final form consisted of (45) items, where the highest score (201) and the lowest score (119). And the hypothetical mean (135).</i></p> <p><i>As for the scale of strategies for coping with stress, the researcher adopted the scale (Shadani, 2011), which consists of six strategies, namely (problem solving strategy (pressure situation), (support and support strategy), (avoidance strategy (withdrawal), (communication strategy), (The strategy of adopting the traditional pattern), (the strategy of relying on religion and ethics) and its validity and stability were verified by extracting honesty by the method of virtual honesty and construction honesty, and the researcher concluded that the contribution of a sense of cohesion in explaining the variation in strategies for coping with stress among kindergarten teachers was at different levels.</i></p>

Introduction

Stress is one of the problems associated with contemporary life, which is witnessing social, economic, professional changes and other rapid problems of progress and tremendous development, which judge societies to adapt to their various requirements. Teachers faced during their work in the teaching profession, especially kindergarten teachers, as they deal with an important segment of society and they are children, a lot of external and internal pressures (Utair, 2019: 4-6); as a result of various problems and various ambitions, teachers were forced to exert more effort and continuous work, which was reflected in negative effects on their health, giving and their efficiency in performance (Jadallah, 2002: 30).

For this reason, teachers in general, and kindergarten teachers in particular, seek in emotional ways first to find ways to address and resist pressures in order to adapt, and these methods are represented in strategies to confront

pressures (Al-Hamid, 2008: 16); The results of a study indicate that adopting effective coping strategies helps maintain a level of mental health and the absence of emotional disturbances, and vice versa (Mohammed, 2019: 137).

Confrontation strategies are among the methods and methods that the individual uses consciously and consciously, and employs them in positive dealing with sources of anxiety or an event that causes psychological hardship or trauma; Individuals differ in their selection and use of coping strategies in stressful situations. If the stressful situation is effective, it results in less description of health disorders (Damtchev 28: 1989).

According to Lazarus & Folkman, (1984) inquiry, that individuals are not just victims of stress, but how they appreciate and perceive stressful situations, and how they build their abilities and strategies to deal with those situations that determine the quality of the influential element and the nature of stress (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984: 3).

Therefore, individuals who choose effective and appropriate strategies in order to confront and overcome certain pressures are individuals who can enjoy cohesion, as they consider the tasks entrusted to them or that they face as motivating rather than tiring (Youssef, 2017: 64). Thus, the results of the study (Barzwan, 2014) showed that effective coping strategies are effective through estimating and evaluating the individual's accurate knowledge of the stressful situation and choosing the appropriate strategy for him (Barzwan, 2014: 105).

Based on the foregoing, it is necessary to search for the possible relationship between the sense of cohesion that female teachers carry as they are important segments of society, and the result that can appear in the behavior, which are strategies for coping with pressure, so the research problem can be determined by the following question:

-Is there a correlation between a sense of cohesion and strategies for coping with stress among kindergarten teachers?

The Importance of the Research

The increasing demands of life are a result of the continuous rapid change which the world is witnessing today; Which contributed to the exposure of individuals to a high degree of pressure, the results of which were reflected on individuals and societies (Buchanan & Driscoll, 2010:9); the events of daily life carry with them the pressures that the individual does not realize except when he constantly keeps pace with different situations at work or dealings with people or problems for which he does not find suitable solutions, and they need a higher degree of coping for the purpose of cohesion and harmony (Davidon, 1983: 616).

Therefore, the kindergarten teacher is one of the most important segments of the educational process in kindergartens, and she is the mainstay of the country and its true revolution; Which soon assume the responsibility for building society and its progress through the development and education of children, and in this regard, the results of the study (Becker, 1987) indicate that the pressures facing the individual increase his psychological problems and increase their impact on the mental, psychological and physical aspects, which generates a deficit and failure in facing them, and it becomes personal Frustrated and troubled (Becker, 1987:5). The sense of cohesion represents what includes granting a life through which the individual can face challenges that are worth investing effort because the lack of meaning of life is linked to some psychological disorders, while the presence of a positive meaning of life has a strong link to dedicating effort to success, the value of life and clarity of goals as well as its connection to physical health and psychological

Based on the foregoing, it is possible to limit the theoretical and practical importance of the research;

The theoretical significance is determined by the following:

1. They show the importance of the current research from the nature of the variables it addressed, namely (a sense of cohesion and strategies for coping with pressures); This research topic is a relatively recent topic, as the researcher has not been able to obtain any previous study based on determining the relationship between the two variables to be studied.
2. for the importance of the research sample represented by kindergarten teachers and their important role in serving the community and promoting the education and education of children, and highlighting the aspects that would increase adherence to the selected strategies in the face of life pressures in order to achieve health and psychological, physical and behavioral balance.
3. Presenting a theoretical framework for the following research variables (a sense of cohesion and strategies for coping with stress) and highlighting them for the purpose of enriching the educational and psychological library in general with theoretical information for these two variables, and filling the two gaps, even if it is a partial thing, which enables students in the field of general psychology and educational sciences And psychological and psychological counseling benefit from.
4. Scarcity and lack of Iraqi and Arab research that dealt with the relationship between female teachers' sense of cohesion and strategies for coping with stress are observed.

Research Objectives

The current research aims to identify:

1. A sense of cohesion among kindergarten teachers.
2. Strategies for coping with the pressures of kindergarten teachers.
3. The direction and strength of the correlative relationship between a sense of cohesion and strategies for coping with pressures among kindergarten teachers.
4. The significance of the difference in the correlation between a sense of cohesion and strategies for coping with stress among kindergarten teachers according to the variables of social status (married - unmarried), and years of service (10 years and less - more than 10 years).
5. The extent to which the sense of cohesion contributes to strategies for coping with pressures among kindergarten teachers.

Research Limits

The current research is determined by:

Human limits: Kindergarten teachers.

Spatial boundaries: the governmental kindergartens that belong to the General Directorate of Education in Baghdad Governorate, Al-Rusafa and Al-Karkh.

Time limits: 2020-2021.

Scientific limits: a sense of cohesion, and strategies for coping with pressures.

Define Terminology

First: Sense of cohesion is defined by:

Antonovsky, (1979-10): It is an orientation towards life that expresses the extent to which a person possesses an urgent or acute, stable and dynamic feeling at the same time of reassurance, so that the requirements coming from the external and internal world of experiences become clear or employed in the course of life and predictable. And interpretation, and the necessary resources are available in order to meet the requirements, and that these requirements are challenges worthy of sacrifice and commitment.

Consoli, (1993): It is a general direction of thinking centered around a constant and dynamic sense of self-confidence, which allows a person to understand and control stimuli coming from the external or internal environment, in order to confront and address stressful situations, (Jolly, 2002:78).

Khalil, (2004:6): It is a positive image of the self that is capable of dealing and overcoming the requirements and difficulties of internal and external life, while possessing self-confidence in the ability to manage and arrange the conditions of this life, and achieve balance and conformity between the conditions and needs.

Theoretical definition: where the researcher adopted the definition (Antonovsky; 1979) for its suitability for the purposes and objectives of the current research, in addition to its adoption of his theory in constructing the scale.

Procedural definition: It is the total score obtained by the teacher after answering the items of the Sense of Coherence Scale.

Second: Strategies for coping with stress

-Lazarus&Folkman, (1984): state that it is the constant cognitive and behavioral efforts to change or deal with internal or external requirements that exceed the individual's abilities to understand these demands and reduce or make them more likely (Lazarus&Folkman, 1984: 20).

-Fotni, (1994): Dealing in a rational manner in the face of stressful stimuli so as to reduce the psychological and physical effects resulting from it (Fotni, 1994: 96).

Theoretical definition: The researcher has identified a definition (Lazarus&Folkman, 1984) for its suitability for the purposes and objectives of the current research, in addition to their adoption of their theory in the scale.

Procedural definition: where it is the total score obtained by the teacher after their answers to the paragraphs of the Strategies Coping with Stress Scale.

Third: Kindergarten teacher

-Ministry of Education, (1991): as a professional educator in the field of child rearing before primary school, where she works on raising and protecting children, providing them with sound health care, and contributing a great deal to the comprehensive development of the child's personality, physically, mentally, emotionally, socially, linguistically, behaviorally and religiously (Ministry of Education 1991: 5).

Theoretical framework and previous studies

Sense of Cohesion

The emergence of a sense of cohesion

After the fifties of the twentieth century, a new trend appeared in psychology, which is positive psychology, which is directed towards studying the impact of psychological variables on the health status, discovering the factors that develop and maintain human health, and not focusing on mental disorders and diseases (Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000:99). It is very important for society to investigate how to deal with stress and avoid stresses that can represent chaos such as violence, war, etc., and as an opposite of this chaos Antonovsky has raised another way to reach health to manage dealing with and adapt to the chaos of life (95: Mittelmark, et al, 2016).

Through a series of research papers on health and disease, Antonovsky sought to understand the mechanism by which some people remain healthy in a world full of stress. According to him, this concept is considered an internal resource for the enjoyment of health, as most of his work on this subject came through his attempt to identify and understand how individuals act from the sources of stress in their surroundings, and he also tried to understand the factors that make some people healthy in a world full of causes of stress. (Human Resources Development Journal, 2018: 180).

The importance of a sense of cohesion in one's life

1. It represents a sense of cohesion, including the meaning of life that an individual can through facing challenges that deserve an investment of effort, because the lack of the meaning of life is linked to some psychological disorders, while the presence of a positive meaning of life has a strong link to dedicating effort to success, the value of life and clarity of goals as well as its connection to health Physical and psychological (Zikka & Chamberlain, 1992:137).
2. The level of sense of cohesion affects the individual's ability to use the available resources in order to maintain his health and his sense of being better (Youssef, 2017: 63).
3. Individuals who enjoy rich feelings of cohesion choose effective and appropriate strategies in order to confront and overcome certain stresses, and feel that the tasks they face are more motivating than exhausting (Radwan, 2002: 22).
4. The sense of coherence organizes the motives and stimuli of life in its internal and external surroundings in a coordinated, predictable, clarification and interpretation manner (Hamo, 2019: 25).
5. The association of a sense of cohesion (a sense of subjective) with good physical and psychological health, quality of life and satisfaction with it, and good social support to some extent with behavior closer to avoiding risks, and conversely with a decrease in the sense of cohesion (Radwan, 2002: 26).

The characteristics of individuals with a high sense of cohesion can be summarized as follows:

1. They have targeted measures that enhance resources to address the expected harm, and alleviate the disturbing relationship between the individual and his social and physical environment.
2. They are characterized by the ability to reduce bad mood, improve their lives, and get rid of the pressures that fall on them, which helps them to reconcile their requirements and environmental conditions surrounding them, and makes them feel comfortable when the source of the handicap facilitates the satisfaction of their psychological, social and physical needs (Friedland, 1996:96).
3. These individuals enjoy relaxation, confidence and reassurance when they face problems in the future, and without feeling pressure, tension or high excitement (Folkman & Judith, 2000: 656).
4. Individuals who adopt a sense of cohesion in the face of pressures and bruises that they face, their administrations are successful in dealing with psychological problems so as to enable them to confront quickly and adequately, without their behaviors being undesirable (ibid).

Theoretical trends that explain the sense of cohesion

1. Theory 1961_ Young 1875

Young emphasized that it is possible to explain the normal behavior of the individual by focusing on the three main personality systems which are the ego, the personal unconscious, and the collective unconscious; Valana gives the individual a sense of continuity, coherence, and identity as well as the teleological rationale for behavior; It represents the consciousness center of the individual; It is the part that thinks, feels, feels and creates possibilities and accesses memory to consciously retrieve memories and past experiences. It is the link between our inner and outer world, and the personal unconscious and collective unconscious provide the individual with causal justifications for behavior (Al-Khalidi, 2000: 96).

The personal unconscious includes the forgotten and repressed experiences of the history of the individual, which are in the form of compounds or knots, while the collective unconscious includes the ways and things in the human formation that all people share (Engler, 1999: 97).

2. Rational Emotional therapy theory, 1955

This cognitive theory, which is based on the groundwork of the idea that what people think and say about themselves, as well as their attitudes, opinions, and ideals, are important matters closely related to their healthy and sick behavior. And he believes that knowledge and emotion are very closely related, and that controlling an individual's thoughts is providing control over his emotions (Yasin, 2012: 45).

Ellis believes that the early false, neurotic, or illogical experiences persist and do not extinguish despite the fact that they are not reinforced from the outside because individuals reinforce these learned experiences by repeating them internally for themselves until they become a philosophy for them and a view of their own. The characteristics of mental health are:

1. Self-interest: the individual should take care of himself first, but without selfishness.
2. Self-direction: The person has to take personal responsibility and work efficiently.
3. Tolerance: A person should not bear the mistakes of others.
4. Acceptance of Uncertainty: A person must accept the fact that he lives in a world of possibilities.
5. Flexibility: The average person is characterized by flexibility in thinking, and he accepts change.
6. Scientific Thinking: The average person is characterized by being objective and logical.
7. Commitment: People are usually interested and preoccupied with different things.
8. Risk Taking: The average person has an adventurous spirit.
9. Self-Acceptance: The average person is content with his life, satisfied with himself.
10. Non-Utopianism: We all face frustration, regret or regret, this is the nature of life. (Abdul-Raouf and Suleiman, 2006: 50).

3. Salutogenerer theory, 1979:

The theory of health origin, which was postulated by the medical sociologist AntonovskyArwn in 1979, is one of the most important discoveries in health psychology, which looks at health as a continuous movement between the enjoyment of full health and complete ill health. Situational factors such as personal awareness of environmental stresses, and the individual's awareness of the social support that supported him in stressful situations, which can describe the ability to manage psychological stress factors, which stick to indicators and conclusions drawn from the framework in us every day, and this was known as a sense of cohesion (Antonovske, 1979: 107).

Research Methodology

The researcher used the descriptive correlative method in the research. Where the descriptive approach is considered the most expressive of this approach, and it is one of the most widespread and common approaches in educational and human sciences research, which is concerned with revealing the relationships between the two variables or more than one variable (Abbas et al., 2014: 76); Correlational research that describes the degree of relationships between variables quantitatively and qualitatively; Because the purpose of data collection is to determine the degree between the variables to which the variables are quantitatively linked to each other (Abu Allam, 2006: 239).

The Research Community

Where the current research community knows that all individuals or things who constitute an important topic or research problem and that all elements related to the research problem that the researcher sought to generalize the results of the study (Abbas et al., 2014: 216), the research community has been identified and represented by kindergarten teachers in the General Directorates of Education in the governorates of Baghdad (Rusafa First, Rusafa Second, Rusafa Third - First Karkh, Second Karkh, Third Karkh), and after obtaining the preparation of teachers from the Directorates of Education / Statistics Division for the year (2020-2021) as in Annex (2) shows that their numbers (1948) are teachers distributed according to the districts. Table 1 illustrates this.

Table (1)

The research community is distributed according to the districts of education in Baghdad governorate

Ratios	No. of Teachers	No. of Kindergarten	Directorates
(%30.21)	415	28	Rusafa First
(%10.25)	489	54	Rusafa Second
(%62.8)	168	20	Rusafa Third

(%96.17)	350	32	First Karkh
(%85.9)	192	21	Karkh Second
(%14.17)	334	30	Third Karkh
	1948	185	Total

Third: Research Data

The Data is part of the community on which the current research is conducted, and it is chosen by the researcher to conduct his research according to special rules and methodology in order to represent the community correctly (Al-Azzawi, 2008: 161), where the method of choosing the researcher for the sample is one of the important scientific and methodological steps in the research, Which reveals the extent of consistency and interdependence between the research problem and its objectives (Melhem, 2002: 137), and the research samples will be presented as follows:

a.Data of Statistical Analysis

The researcher chose a stratified random sample of the appropriate type of distribution in order to become identical for the different classes in the current original society; a sample of (400) female teachers was selected, with a percentage of (53, 20%) from the research community, distributed according to the general directorates of education in the province of Baghdad, and table (2) illustrates this.

Table (2)

Statistical analysis data distributed according to the general directorates of education in Baghdad governorate

Ratios	No. of Teachers	No. of Kindergarten	Directorates
(%75.28)	115	12	Rusafa First
(%25.31)	125	17	Rusafa Second
(%25)	100	15	First Karkh
(%15)	60	13	Third Karkh
(%53.20)	400	57	Total

B: Final Application Sample

The researcher chose a random sample from the class to be representative of the different classes in the original society. A sample of (200) female teachers was selected, with a percentage of (26.10%) from the original research community (1948), distributed by social status and years of service, and Table (3) illustrates this.

Table (3)

Final application sample broken down by marital status/years of service

Sample Size	Percentage	Years of Service	Percentage	Marital Status
100	(%74)	148 Less than 10 years	(%65)	Married 130
100	(%26)	52 More than 10 years	(%35)	Unmarried 70
200	(%100)	200	(%100)	200 /Total

A: A sample survey application

The purpose of using this sample is to find out the clarity of the paragraphs of the search scale, and to calculate the time taken to answer the parameters; Therefore, the researcher chose a random sample of (30) teachers.

Fourth: The Search Tools

To achieve the objectives of the research, the researcher built a scale and adopted another scale, as follows:

First: The measure of the sense of cohesion:

In order to achieve the preparation of the paragraphs of the sense of coherence scale according to the theoretical definition adopted by the researcher, and after reviewing the literature and a number of studies and scientific standards that are related to the topic, including (Al-Kinani, 2018 - Mustafa, 2019), and for the purpose of verifying the objectives of the research, the researcher built a measure of sense of cohesion appropriate for the Iraqi environment and society sampled by the research represented by kindergarten teachers. The researcher resorted to practical steps to build the scale, as follows:

Scale Building Procedures

A. Theoretical and methodological premises for building the scale

What was presented in the theoretical framework and previous studies of the research, through which the concepts of research and the nature of the approved method are determined, the researcher relied on building the scale on:

-The logical (rational) approach: In this approach, it was based on Antonovsky's theory 1979 as a theoretical framework for the sense of coherence.

-Experimental Approach: This approach relied on observations of methods and behavior and its measurement in specific and highly specific situations that are prepared in advance (Al-Kubaisi, 1987: 47-49), and the researcher relied by adopting the definition (theoretical definition) of ArwnAntonovsky's 1979 theory, the theoretical framework and previous studies Within the domain in determining the components of a sense of cohesion.

B - Defining the concept of a sense of cohesion:

The definition of a sense of coherence has been relied upon according to Antonovsky's theory 1979, which defines a sense of cohesion as an orientation towards life that expresses the extent to which a person has a sense of urgency or acute, stable and dynamic at the same time of reassurance, so that the next requirements become From the world of external and internal experiences that are clear or employed in the course of life and are predictable and interpretable, and the necessary resources are available in order to meet the requirements, and that these requirements are challenges worthy of sacrifice and commitment (Antonovsky, 1979:10).

C. Components of the sense of coherence: The components of the scale were determined by Antonovsky's theory, 1979, which are:

1. Feelings of comprehensibility

The cognitive component is the individual's expectations or skill in being able to represent stimuli or stimuli even unknown to him as coherent and organized information, not confused, random and unclear stimuli. The feelings of clarity mean a cognitive pattern of representation, that is, the individual can understand events in his life and rationally predict what will happen in his life in the future (Antonovsky, 1979: 35).

2. Feelings of manageability

The material component describes the individual's convictions, and that the difficulties are solvable. It is called instrumental confidence. It expresses the extent to which the individual realizes that he has the appropriate reserves or resources and special competencies in order to meet the requirements as well as the belief that others can provide support, and the individual who lacks this belief is like Unfortunate luck who always feels that he is at the mercy of unfortunate events without being able to do anything about them (Antonovsky, 1979:36)).

3. Feelings of meaningfulness

The motivation component considers and describes the extent to which the individual feels emotionally about life as meaningful, so that some of the problems and requirements facing the individual deserve to be harnessed energy, and to make effort and feel obligated around them and that they are welcome challenges rather than annoying challenges that he wants to get rid of Including Antonovsky, 1979: 36-37)).

D. Prepare scale paragraphs

After defining the components of the scale, and defining each component, the researcher prepared the paragraphs after reviewing the literature and previous studies that she reviewed; As the scale consisted of (45) items distributed among the three components of the scale at the rate of (15) items for each component (4), and the items were prepared in a manner that takes into account the presence of the feature and the clarity of the content of the paragraph, and the paragraph includes one idea (Al-Zoba'i and others, 1981: 19).

E. Validity of scale items (logical analysis of scale items)

This procedure requires obtaining consensus of a group of experts about the validity of the scale; Therefore, the researcher presented the paragraphs of the sense of coherence scale to a group of experts and arbitrators specialized in educational and psychological sciences, specialists in the kindergarten department and specialists in measurement and evaluation (Appendix 6)), and they gave their opinions and advice on the validity of the paragraphs in terms of:-

1. The validity of each paragraph of the scale.
2. Clarity of the mechanisms of instructions.
3. Make modifications to the metaphors, such as deletion and addition.

In order to ensure the validity of the scale's paragraphs, the scale was presented in its initial form consisting of (45) paragraphs of supplement (4) to a group of arbitrators and experts, whose number reached (10) arbitrators or experts.

This is what specialists in the field of educational research and psychological sciences refer to the need to seek the assistance of With the opinions of the arbitrators to verify the validity of the tool, and this included a presentation of the theoretical definition on which the researcher relied and the definition of each of its components. What it was set for, and the appropriateness of each paragraph of the component to which it belongs, and the validity of all alternatives, leaving the arbitrators the possibility of adding and deleting paragraphs.

Then suggesting the appropriate amendment to it for any paragraph that needed that; In what may make the scale more suitable for the current research sample, and after retrieving the questionnaire of arbitrators and experts and analyzing the valuable opinions of experts on the scale items, the KA2 test was used for one sample and each item was considered valid when the calculated chi-square value is a function at the level (0.05).

Where the literature of psychological and educational measurement indicated that the analysis of test items leads to improving its quality by discovering positions of weakness and positions of strength in it, reformulating it, and excluding the invalid from it; Therefore, the objective of the analysis is to verify the validity of the scale items and improve their quality. Therefore, the researcher proceeded to the statistical analysis of the items of the scale of strategies for coping with stress as follows.

First: the discriminatory power of paragraphs

To analyze the extent of the paragraphs of the stress coping strategies scale according to this method, the researcher applied the scale to the statistical analysis sample of (400) parameters and adopted the following steps:

1. It is to find the total score for each form after correcting it and ensuring its validity.
2. The total scores extracted from the (400) forms are arranged in descending order from the highest score to the lowest score.
3. A percentage of (27%) from the upper group was chosen to represent the upper group and a percentage (27%) from the lower group to represent the lower group to identify two extreme groups with the largest size and maximum variance. The number of forms for members of the upper group is (108) forms and the number of forms for members of the lower group was (108) forms, and thus we have the largest possible size and maximum variance and their distribution is close to the normal distribution (Anastasi, 1976: 208).
4. The T-test for two independent samples was used to test the significance of the differences between the average scores of the upper and lower groups for each item, and to compare the calculated T-value for each item with the tabular value of (1.96) at the significance level (0.05) and the degree of freedom (214), and Table (11) illustrates this.

Table (11)

The differential power of the paragraphs of the problem-solving strategy (pressure situation)

calculated T value	lower group		higher group		Seq. Paragraph
	Standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	
11,008	0,836	2,86	0,819	4,10	1
9,535	1,030	2,94	0,890	4,19	2
11,105	0,872	2,87	0,752	4,11	3
8,581	0,990	2,90	0,842	3,98	4
9,157	1,009	3,99	0,840	4,14	5
2,910	1,033	3,25	1,024	3,65	6
9,772	0,870	2,99	0,828	4,12	7
8,324	0,941	3,04	0,872	4,07	8

Psychometric Properties of the Vertebrae of the Scale

The psychometric characteristics of the scale items included that the scale's ability to measure what it was prepared to measure and psychometric specialists agree that honesty and stability are the two most important characteristics of the psychometric characteristics of the scale items.

First: Validity of the scale

Check in the scale of strategies for coping with pressures of honesty:

a. Face Validity

Where this type of apparent honesty of the stress coping strategies scale was achieved through what was presented in its initial form consisting of (35) paragraphs of annex (5) and on a group of arbitrators and experts specialized in psychological measurement, science, educational, psychological and kindergarten, whose number is (10) arbitrators. (6) To assess the validity and appropriateness of the paragraphs, instructions and alternatives of the scale; the paragraphs of the scale were approved by all arbitrators.

B. Construct Validity

The construction validity has been used a lot in the experimental verification of the extent to which the scale scores match the concepts on which the researcher is based in building the scale, and when the experimental results

match the assumptions, and this also indicates the validity of the construction in the scale (Helmstader, 1966: 134), and the construction validity has been verified. From the sincerity of constructing the stress coping strategies scale through the discriminatory power of the paragraphs, and the internal consistency represented by the correlation of the degree of the paragraph with the total degree of the strategy to which it belongs.

Second: Reliability of scale

One of the most important steps in psychological scales and educational sciences is to calculate the stability of the scale with honesty, as it indicates the accuracy of the scale, its stability, and the consistency of its paragraphs in measuring what was prepared to measure it (Fransella, 1981: 91), so the researcher verified the stability of the scale of strategies for coping with stress in two ways:

a. Test-Retest method

Calculating the stability in this way, which is called the stability coefficient over time, requires re-applying the scale to the same stability sample with a time difference; Therefore, the stress coping strategies scale was applied again on the same stability sample of (40) kindergarten teachers who were randomly selected after two weeks.

After the completion of the application, the stability of each of the strategies of coping with stress was calculated by calculating the degrees of this sample in the second application with their degrees in the first application, and using the Pearson Correlation coefficient between the degrees of the two applications, and Table (18) illustrates this.

Table (18)

The stability coefficient for each of the strategies for coping with stress

Stability Coefficient	Strategies
0,84	Problem Solving (positionStress)
0,83	Support (correlation)
0,80	Avoidance (withdrawal)
0,81	Communications
0,82	Adopting the traditional style
0,83	Dependence on religion and morals

Table (18) shows that all values are highly stable

B. Alfakrobnach equation (for internal consistency)

In order to extract stability according to this method, each degree of the statistical analysis sample, which amounted to (400) forms, was subjected to the Cronbach's alpha equation, and the table (19) shows the Facronbach stability coefficient for each strategy.

Table (19)

The stability coefficient for each of the strategies for coping with stress

Stability Coefficient	Strategies
0,82	Problem Solving (positionStress)

0,81	Support (correlation)
0,79	Avoidance (withdrawal)
0,80	Communication
0,80	adopting traditional style
0,81	Dependence on religion and morals

The stress coping strategies scale in its final form:

The stress coping strategies scale consists of (35) items distributed over six domains, and by (8) items for strategies focused on solving the problem (pressure situation), (7) for support and support strategies, (5) for avoidance and withdrawal strategy, and (4) For the communication strategy, and (7) the strategy of adopting the traditional style, and (4) for the strategies of relying on religion and morals, and graded five (always, often, sometimes, rarely, never), and with degrees (5_1) for the positive direction of the paragraph, and degrees (1_5) for the negative direction For the paragraph.

Fifth: The final application of the two search criteria:

In order to achieve the objectives of the current research, after the two scales became ready and suitable for application on the members of the current research sample, the researcher applied the measure of sense of cohesion in its final form and the scale of strategies for coping with stress in its final form, simultaneously on the members of the current research sample consisting of (200) female teachers were selected in a stratified random manner from the directorates affiliated with Rusafa / Karkh, and the researcher was keen to apply the two scales themselves, as the application period was from (12/14/2020) to (7/1/2021).

Statistical means:

The researcher used the appropriate statistical means through the use of the statistical bag for social sciences (SPSS) in the procedures for verifying the psychometric properties of the research scales and research objectives to reach the results, as follows:

1_ Chi-square (Ka2): It is to find out what is the significance of the difference in the opinions of experts on the paragraphs of the two scales of the current research.

2_ T-test for two independent samples: It is to calculate the discriminatory power of the items of the two standards of the current research.

3_ Pearson correlation coefficient: It is to extract honesty, represented by the paragraph's relationship with the total score, the paragraph's relationship with strategies facing pressure, the relationship of strategies with other strategies and other areas and with the total degree of the scale, and to calculate the stability (retest method) for the two research standards, and to calculate the direction, strength and weakness of the relationship between the current research variables.

4_ Cronbach's Alpha equation: It is to calculate the stability of the two current research scales.

5_ One-sample T-test: It is to find out what the level of the research variables among the members of the current research sample.

6_ The Z-test for the significance of a coefficient for the correlation of the two variables of the current research is used.

7_ Syntactic test: to extract the differences in the correlational relationship between the research variables according to the study stage.

8_ Simple linear regression analysis: It is to know the extent to which the sense of cohesion contributes to strategies for coping with stress.

Conclusions

The results of the current research indicated that the following can be concluded:

1. The current research sample has a sense of coherence based on the differences between the arithmetic mean and the hypothetical mean.

2. The current research sample has high stress coping strategies based on the differences between the arithmetic mean and the hypothetical mean; Where they use at a high level the strategies of (problem solving, support and (support), and dependence on religion and morals), and they use at an average level the strategies of (avoidance (withdrawal), communication, and adopting the traditional pattern).

3. There is a positive, direct, statistically significant correlation between a sense of cohesion and strategies for coping with stress, each of (solving the problem, avoidance (withdrawal), communication, adoption of the traditional pattern, and dependence on religion and morals), and a positive, non-significant correlation for the strategy of avoidance (withdrawal).

4. There are differences in the associative relationship between the sense of cohesion and the strategies of (problem solving, support, adopting the traditional style, and relying on religion and morals) according to the social status (married - unmarried) and in favor of married women, and there are no differences in the correlation Between a sense of cohesion and two strategies (avoidance (withdrawal), and communication) according to social status (married - unmarried).

5. There are differences in the correlation between the sense of cohesion and the strategies of each of (problem solving, support, and dependence on religion and morals) according to the years of service (10 years and less - more than 10 years) and in favor of more than 10 years, and there is no Differences in the correlation between a sense of cohesion and the strategies of (avoidance (withdrawal), communication, and adopting the traditional style) according to the years of service (10 years and less - more than 10 years).

6. The contribution of a sense of cohesion in explaining the variation in strategies for coping with pressures among kindergarten teachers represents:

1. The effect of the sense of coherence on the variance of the problem-solving strategy was 1.31%.

2. The effect of the sense of cohesion on the variation in the support strategy was 43.8%.

3. The effect of the sense of cohesion is weak in the variable of avoidance strategy (withdrawal) was 1.1%.

4. The effect of the sense of cohesion on the variation in the communication strategy was 7.8%.

5. The effect of the sense of cohesion on the variation in the strategy of adopting the traditional pattern was 3.17%.

6. The effect of the sense of coherence on the variance of the strategy of reliance on religion and morals was 3.25%.

Recommendations:

Conclusions of the current research The researcher recommends the following:

1. Utilizing the two standards of current research by the Ministry of Education to set up guidance programmes, open training courses, and hold scientific and cultural seminars, all of which aim to develop a sense of cohesion and strategies for coping with pressures for its cadres in general and kindergarten cadres in particular.

2. Investing and operating the two search criteria by researchers to conduct more research and studies.

3. Emphasis on the importance of cohesion to face the pressures of life in the curricula of colleges and institutes from which female teachers graduate because of its importance in building their psychological, health and scientific personalities.

4. The media reinforce the sense of psychological cohesion among individuals in general and educational cadres in particular, as well as raising awareness of stressful situations that they may face in their professional and non-professional lives to identify the best strategy in dealing with pressures.

Suggestions

In light of the research recommendations, the researcher suggests the following:

1. Conducting a study similar to the research on samples that may be different and comparing its results with the results of the current research.
2. Building educational programs to develop a sense of cohesion among kindergarten teachers or students.
- 3 . Conducting studies dealing with the sense of cohesion and its relationship to some other variables (such as enjoyment of life, strength of will, and others).
- 4 . Pointing a comparative study between strategies for coping with stress for kindergarten teachers in public and private kindergartens,
- 5 . Piloting a study dealing with the strategy of coping with stress and its relationship to some other variables such as (self-confidence, methods of socialization, psychological hardness, personal guidance and others).

References

- Al-Azzawi, Rahim Younis (2008): An Introduction to the Scientific Research Method, 1st Edition, Dar Degla Publishers and Distributors, Amman.
- Abbas, Muhammad Khalil, Nofal, Muhammad Bakr, al-Absi, Muhammad Mustafa, Abu Awwad Faryal Muhammad (2014) Introduction to Research Methods in Education and Psychology, 5th edition, Dar Al-Maysara for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan.
- Al-Kinani, Muj Zia Hussein (2018): A sense of cohesion and its relationship to psychological well-being, Master's thesis, College of Arts, Department of Psychology, Al-Mustansiriya University.
- Antonovsky , A.(1979) . Apenbixa :sense of coherence scale Antonovsky . Journal of health psychology .
- Antonovsky , A.(1987) . Apenbixa :sense of coherence scale Antonovsky . Journal of health psychology .
- Antonovsky , A .(1993) the salntogenic .Cecture held in Berkely , danury 21.
- Antonovsky . (1987) .Vnravaling the mystery of health . How people manage stress and stay well .sanfranciso : drssey – Bass puplishers
- Antonovsky, A. (1987). Apenbixa: Sense1Antonovsky .journal of health psychology.
- Antonovsky, A. (1988). Unraveling the mystery of health. How people manage stress and stay well. San Francisco: jossey-Bass publishers.
- Antonovsky, A. (1993). The salutogenic approach to aging. Lecture held in Berkeley, January 21,1993.
- Barzwan, Haseba, (2016): The effectiveness of confrontation strategies in managing psychological stress. Journal of Human and Social Sciences, Issue (24), University of Algiers.
- Buchanan, T. W., Driscoll,D., Mowrer, S. MSollers, J.J, Thayer J. F., Kirschbaum,C.,&Tranel, D. (2010). Medial prefrontal cortex damage affect ts physiological and psychological stress responses differently in men.
- Consoli (1993) : coping strategies of university students with Learuing disabilities . johrnal of learning .
- Damtchev,N (1989): strategie de coping et pattern A, Revue de med, psychologiqueDebre.
- Davidon, We missed (1999): Overcome technical pressures and start life, translated by Hamad Al-Farmawi, Rakha Abu Saree, Anglo-Egyptian Library, Cairo.
- Davidon, Linda (1983): Contributions of social work in the field of caring for special groups, the modern university office.
- Folkman , S ,Lazarus R (1980) An analysis of coping in amiddle ageing community sample . Journal of health and social Behavior ,.
- Folkman , S(2002) : Levels of intriasic motivation and its correlates with iorel of personal controlling process , Journal of applied psychology .
- Folkman , S. Greer , S. (2000) Promting Psychological Well – Being in the face of Serious illnss ; whwn theory Research and Practieein form Eah other . Journal Articaie ,nol 9,1.
- Folkman, S. & Greer, S. (2000). Promoting psychological well-Being in the face of serious illness: when theory, research and practice in form each other. Journal Article, vol (1).
- Folkman, S. & Lazarus, R. (1980). An analysis of coping in amiddle ageing community sample. Journal or health and social Behavior,120.
- Folkman, S. &Greer, S. promoting psychological well-being in the face of serious illness: when theory research and practice inform each other. Journal Article, vol (1).
- Folkman, S.,& Lazarus, R.S.(1988). Coping as amediator of emo- tion .journal of personality and social psychology.
- Radwan, SamerJabal, (2002): Mental Health, Dar Al-Masira, Jordan, 3rd edition.
- Lazarus , R, folkman , S(1987) : stress Appraisal and coping , new York .
- Lazarus&Folkman (1984): An analysis of coping in amiddle ageing community sample .Journal of health and social Behavior.
- Lazaus, Richard (1989): The Personality, translated by SayedGhoneim, 3rd edition, Dar Al-Shorouk, Cairo.
- Muhammad Salih Abdul-Raouf, Ahmed Suleiman, (2006): Introduction to Mental Health, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Al-Rasheed Library.

- Mustafa, Shahd Muhammad, (2019): Feelings of cohesion and their relationship to social frustration levels for female students of the Kindergarten Department, University of Baghdad, College of Education for Girls, a master's thesis (unpublished), Baghdad.
- Melhem, Sami Muhammad (2009): Measurement and evaluation in education and psychology, Dar Al-Maysara, for publication, distribution and printing.
- Jolly,R. N., Tsai, P. ch.&chen, l. (2016). Sense of coherence among older Adult Residents of long. Term care facilities in Taiwan: Across sectional Analysis. Journal Research Articie, Dol.
- Seligman ,M. (2002) : Using the new positive psychology to realize your potentol for lasting fulfillment . ivewgork: free press.
- Shadani, Omar (2011): Strategies for coping with psychological stress in the school environment among teachers of the primary stage in Bouira, unpublished master's thesis.
- Yousefi, Hadda (2018): Feelings of healthy psychological cohesion for the prevention of psychological stress, social studies and research, Al-Shaheed University.
- Zikka,C., &Tezer, E (1992) The role of sense of coherence and physical activity in positive and negative affect of Turkishadolescents.

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